

ULUSLARARASI SOSYAL BİLİMLER KONGRESİ

INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS OF SOCIAL SCIENCE

TAM METİN BİLDİRİLER KİTABI
CONGRESS PROCEEDINGS BOOK

14-17

Eylül/September

**Diyarbakır
TURKEY 2017**

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Şarkiyat ICSS'17

International Congress of Social Science

Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi Tam Metin Bildiriler Kitabı

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Şarkiyat Bilim ve Hikmet Vakfı Yayınıdır

Yenişehir Yıldız Sokak No: 5 21100
Yenişehir/Diyarbakır

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14-17 Eylül tarihlerinde Şarkiyat Vakfı, Şarkiyat Araştırmaları Derneği ve e-Şarkiyat İlmi Araştırmalar Dergisi tarafından Diyarbakır'da tertiplenen Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi'nde sunulan bildirilerin tam metinlerini içermektedir.

Aralık 2017
ISBN: 978-605-67961-1-1

Arrival of Turk Khan Jahan in Southern Bengal and Flourish of Mosque Architecture

Abu Bakkar Siddique*

Abstract

1204 A.D. is the most important year in history of the Muslim Bengal. This year were conquered the Bengal by the Turk valiant Ikhtiyar Uddin Mohammad bin Bakhtiyar Khilji. Afterwards many Muslim dynasty rules in this area for long period and most of the rulers among them are Turk ethnic who come from the Central Asia. At first stage Gour, Loukhnouti and Pandua become a most significant place where governors were appointed by the Delhi sovereigns. In centering these places of Bengal begin to develop the Islamic tradition against the Hindu and Buddhist culture. Those time a lot of Turk origin particularly sufi, saint Came in this region to spread of Islam as well as they also brought architectural techniques on Islamic architecture of Bengal. Basically, Bengal is separated from Delhi sovereigns in 1338 A.D. by declaring the independence of Fakhr Al-Din Mubarak Shah and which continue upto 1538 A.D. A vast number of Mosques were built during this period. In fifteenth century, When the sultan Nasiruddin Mahmud Shah I(Founder of the second Ilyas Shahi dynasty) was ruling at Gour, The pioneer saint Turk Khan Jahan Ali comes on the southern part of Bengal or forest area of Sundarban and founds some townships, builds mosques, tomb, madrasas and sarais, roads, highways, bridges and a large number of dighis (pond) in the mentioning part. Now it includes the Bagherhat, Khulna, Satkhira, Jessore, Jhenaidah, Patuakhali and Barishal districts of Bangladesh. In which he flourished the Islamic culture specially mosque architecture. He added a new architectural feature in mosque that is called Khan Jahan style in Bengal architecture. In this paper have been marked that how patron saint Khan Jahan Ali arrives an uncultivated land and develops with Islamic culture by establishing his fascinating mosque architecture in the greater part of the southern Bengal.

Keywords: Bengal, Turk, Khan Jahan, Islamic culture, Mosque architectur

Khan Jahan Ali

There is no more information about Khan Jahan's personal life. According to historians he was a noble man of Turkish family and took training in Turkish, Arabic and Islamic science in his early life. Afterword he comes in Delhi and pursues a career under the Tughlaqs Sultan (Khan, 2013, 30). The only inscription

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on tomb refers that he died on 25 October 1459 A.D. (27 Jilhajj 863 A.H.) and entitled 'Ulugh Khan and Khan-i-Azam.' The word "Ulugh" (Leader) before his name indicates of his Uzbek origin and another title "Khan-i-Azam (Great)" defines that he was an officer under the Sultan Nasiruddin Mahmud Shah 1 of Bengal. Actually Khan Jahan Ali was a Muslim Sufi Saint and regional ruler in Bagerhat area (now in Bangladesh) in the mid-15th century. It is seems that he comes to Bengal after the sack of Delhi in 1398 A.D. by Amir Timur (Founder of the Timurid dynasty). As a jagir (fief) he obtained the dense forest area of sundarbans from sultans which clearing had been set up for human settlements (Khan, 2006).

Pre-condition of Southern Bengal before Khan Jahan Ali

Although Bengal was conquered in 1204 A.D. by the Ikhtiyaruddin Muhammad Bin Bakhtiyar Khilji and he founded the kingdom including west and north part of Bengal. But the south-eastern part remained beyond the control and influences of Muslim rules more than a hundred years. In 1227 A.D. Ghiasuddin Iwaz Khilji (1212-27) tried to take the control of East Bengal and subsequently in 1236 A.D. Saifuddin Aibak (1233-36) launched another invasion to capture it but both the rulers are failed to achieve success (Siraj, 1983, 28-29). After in 1300 A.D. some area comes under the Muslim rule during the Laukhnauti Sultan Shamsuddin Feroz Shah (1301-22). In 1338 A.D. the Bengal was separated from the Delhi by declaring independence of Sultan Fakhruddin Mubarak Shah. He declared the independence in centering the Sonargaon region that was the center of East Bengal (Karim, 2007, 170). In 1342 A.D the Laukhnauti Sultan Alauddin Ali Shah was defeated and killed by next Sultan Shamsuddin Iliyas Shah. By ascending his throne is commenced the very turning point of Bengal history because in this time Iliyas Shah brought his control among the whole Bengal (Lakhnauti, Shatgaon and Sonargaon) and for that Shams-i-Siraj Afif observed him as Shah-i-Bangalah, Shah-i-Bangaliyan and Sultan-i-Bangalah. (Afif, 1890, 114-118). Iliyas Shah and his descendant including later Iliyas Shahi dynasty ruled Bengal up to 1487 A.D. But the between 1412 to 1435 A.D. for 23 years Hindu Raja Ganesha and his successors Jalaluddin Muhammad Shah (converted to Islam) and Shamsuddin Muhammad Shah ascended the throne of this reign (Chakrabarti, K., and Chakrabarti, S., 2013, 378). In this phase or period of Sultan Ghyasuddin Azam Shah (1390-1411), somewhere Khan Jahan arrived and started taking part in the making history venture of Bengal.

Sultan of Bengal and Khan Jahan Ali

As stated before Khan Jahan Ali comes to Bengal after the sack of Delhi in 1398 A.D. by Amir Timur. According to another source it is said that Sultan of Delhi sent him in the southern or Sundarban area as jagir (fief). Later it had been confirmed by Bengal Sultan. However, this region was totally out of inhabitable and largest mangrove forest in the world (till now) surrounding by dense forest with wild animal. He cleared up the dense jungle and established the human settlement there. In this endeavor named Burhan and Fateh Khan, two deputies of Khan Jahan were industrious efforts to set up of habitation. Pioneer of Islam Khan Jahan gave the Name as "Khalifatabad" (greater Khulna and Jessore) of his newly

human settled area. The word Khalifatabad derived from Arabic Khalifat (Representative). Basically, as an Islam preacher, Sufi and local ruler he works over southern part of Bengal which now it includes the Bagherhat, Khulna, Satkhira, Jessore, Jhenaidah, Patuakhali and Barishal districts of Bangladesh. He founded three township such as Maruli Kasaba, Paigram Kasaba and Bara Bazar besides built some impressive mosques, madrasas, sarais, roads, highways, bridges and a huge number of dighis (pond or tank) (Khan, 2006). During his period Iliyas Shahi dynasty was power of Bengal who promotes for Islamic expansion especially Sultan Nasir Uddin Mahmud Shah 1 (founder of later Iliyas Shahi dynasty) may have directly or indirectly patronizes him. In pursuance of all historians Sultan Nasir Uddin Mahmud 1 was wise and peaceful ruler in Bengal who did not only consolidated his political power but also developed socio-economic enrichment. Likely, Khan Jahan was in the service of Sultan Nasir Uddin Mahmud 1. Although has lack of reliable evidence behind it but following title 'Ulugh Khan and Khan-i-Azam' of Khan Jahan Ali it may be supposed that Sultan awarded these two titles for his great work. (Khan, 2013, 31-32)

Flourish of Mosque Architecture

After consolidation power in the southern territory of Bengal Khan Jahan Ali give the attention to progress of Islamic thoughts and culture. As a result he established a large number of Mosques beside welfare task for his lodger. It is very well known that the Mosque is considered to be the nerve centre of the Muslim society from the beginning of Islam. Mosque was not only the prayer place in the Medieval Bengal as well as it retained function of the Islamic education with its original purpose. Sultans and wealthy persons were built the Mosque in the Muslim inhabited area. Imam who was the teacher alongside the perform prayers in the Mosque. In which people used to learn about Islam such as how to perform prayers, recitation of Holy Quran even they were gathered knowledge in many branches of Islamic studies. Therefore Sufi Saint Khan Jahan play significant role to spread Islamic culture based on the Mosque which contributed to develop of Islamic architecture in the Bengal (Islam, 2016, 13-14).

Khan Jahan Style

Many independent style of mosque architecture has been developed in Bengal for centuries. After Arriving and developing in the Southern Bengal Khan jahan erected a lot of mosque architecture which architectural style was introduced after his named Kahn-e-Jahan style in Bengal. This style was an unusual blending of indigenous techniques with the Tughlaq architectural style of Delhi (Hasan, 1979, 155-156). In according to Percy Brown (1942, 38) as the building materials bricks and terracotta were available joined by lime or mud mortars as well as the techniques were the Hindu construction system of corbelled brick and the bamboo based Chouchala building system. During the ruler and cultural mediator Khan Jahan and his contemporary time plenty of Mosques of this style is founded in Khalifatabad (Bagerhat) and around the largest sundarban area. Later, many mosques are influenced by Khan-e-Jahan style over Bagerhat, Khulna, Jessore, Satkhira, Jhenaidah, Barishal and Potuakhali districts (Dani, 1961, 147). But unfortunately largest portion of these mosques are undated or unknown except Sixty Dome or Sait Gumbad mosque (C 1450), Masjidkur

mosque (C 1450), single dome mosque (1459) adjoining of his own tomb and Masjidbari mosque (1465) (Khan, 2006; Hasan, 1980, 24). There is no doubt that Sixty Dome Mosque is very impressive and largest brick built mosque in Bangladesh among the surviving monuments of the Khan-e-Jahan style (Ahmed, 1984, 138). Along with the Sait Gumbad a group of mosque at the same style is seen at Bagerhat area;

1. Sixty Dome or Sait Gumbad Mosque
2. Tomb Mosque of Khan Jahan
3. Nine domed Mosque
4. Reza Khoda Mosque
5. Zindapir Mosque
6. Ronvijoypur Mosque
7. Singar Mosque
8. Bibi Begni's Mosque
9. Chunikhola Mosque (Hasan, 2011, 3-5). End of the 20th century has ushered a new era to know about Sufi Khan Jahan Ali and his activities in the southern part of Bengal by excavating Barobazar area (Now under the Jhenaidah district). Which Archaeology Department of Bangladesh has identified as the historic 'Mohammadabad city' (A lost Medieval city) and found a group of mosques like Bagerhat in their recent discovery and excavation has been going on around this area. The finding mosques are (till now);

1. Gorar Mosque
2. Golakata Mosque
3. Jore Bangla Mosque
4. Satgachia Mosque
5. Monohor Mosque
6. Pirpukur Mosque
7. Shukur Mollik Mosque
8. Nungola Mosque

9. Pathagar Mosque

10. Singdah Mosque

Most of the mosque of above mentioned are ruined but some of these already have been renovated and others are under process. After restoration of 1992-93 the best conserved mosque is Gorar Mosque. However, to see the excavated mosque in Barobazar, it is said that firstly Saint Khan Jahan Ali settled here before taking place in Khalifatabad (Bagerhat). The central mosque of Barobazar (Now Satgachia Mosque) is multi-domed type like Sait Gumbad Mosque. This Mosque contains 35 domes in which historians have been found more similarities between two mosques as well as considering others mosque's style and date of construction can be said that Barabazar established the Same Sufi pioneer who developed the Khalifatabad region under the southern Bengal (Naqi, 2003, 13-19; Husain, 2007, 139).

Conclusion

Khan Jahan Ali was originally a Sufi and Islam preacher from Central Asia. With the own competence and patronization of sultan, he got the jagir of a jungle region in the southern part of Bengal. Later on, as a local ruler he established human settlement there and for public welfare he also founded roads, towns, mosques, madrasas, sarais, bridges and a lot of dighis (ponds). But in his development activities particularly, the establishment of mosque carries special importance. Because, as these alluring mosques have been promoting the spread of Islam. On the other hand, playing an important role in the development of Muslim architecture even Islamic architecture of Bengal. This style of mosque architecture is observed in various places of subsequent Bengal. In one word, Khan Jahan Ali was a pioneer leader in this territory. That is why historians have described him as a prolific builder for his versatile activities in the southern part of Muslim Bengal (Khan, 2013, 33; Hasan, 2011).

*Figure 1. Sixty Dome Mosque, Bagerhat. Taken from: [Online]. Retrieved from-
<http://www.worldfortravel.com/2013/08/02/sixty-dome-mosque-shat-gambuj-mosque-bangladesh/>*

*Figure 2. Nine dome mosque, Bagerhat. Courtesy: [Mohammad Emran Sarker, 27
May 2016]*

Figure 3. Ronvijoypur mosque, Bagerhat. Source: Online. [http://www.traveladventures.org/continents/asia/bagerhat-mosques06.html]

Figure 4. Singara mosque, Bagerhat. Taken from: [Online]. Retrieved from https://www.pinterest.se/pin/513903007460761465

Figure 5. Gorar mosque, Barobazar, Jhenaidah

Figure 6. Jor Bangla mosque, Barobazar, Jhenaidah

Figure 7. Six Dome Mosque, Barobazar, Jhenaidah

Figure 8. Nungola mosque, Barobazar, Jhenaidah

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